

A 297

12 NOV 1993

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 12 / 11 / 93 TAKE OFF 1004 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A297
 LANDING 1636

PROJECT OFFICER:
 AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE
 FLIGHT LEADER: M. SMITH
 OBSERVER: VACC } C. O'DOWD
 OTHERS: NIGEL (A22)
 2D H. GREENSMITH
 FILTERS D. PERCIVAL
 CCN D. LAUCHLAN.

CAPTAIN: H. BURGOYNE
 CO-PILOT: Steve
 NAVIGATOR: E. HEATON
 ENGINEER: R. PRICE
 LOADMASTER: J. CANNING

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
 OPERATING AREA:

WEST OF IRELAND

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME: 06Z

A297 12 - NOV - 93

GPS data
09:11:34 - 16:37:18

A297 12th November, 1993

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
100439		Take off from FARNBOROUGH		
103011(3)	-112428(5)	Run 1 (in Transit)	FL220	315 deg
113050(7)	-120650(8)	Profile P1	FL220->50ft	240 deg
121137(9)	-121637(10)	Run 2.1	100ft	355 deg
121749(11)	-122248(12)	Run 2.2	100ft	175 deg
122414(13)	-122915(14)	Run 2.3	100ft	355 deg
123023(15)	-123523(16)	Run 2.4	100ft	175 deg
123747(17)	-123948(18)	K-gamma run	100ft	310 deg
124318(19)	-124526(20)	K-gamma reciprocal	100ft	130 deg
124526(20)	-142041(53)	Profile P2	100ft->7500ft	
124935(22)	-125430(23)	Run 3.1	1000ft	355 deg
125550(24)	-130050(25)	Run 3.2	1000ft	175 deg
130212(26)	-130713(27)	Run 3.3	1000ft	355 deg
130837(28)	-131343(29)	Run 3.4	1000ft	175 deg
131558(31)	-132059(32)	Run 4.1	2000ft	355 deg
132219(33)	-132720(34)	Run 4.2	2000ft	175 deg
132833(35)	-133334(36)	Run 4.3	2000ft	355 deg
133456(37)	-133958(38)	Run 4.4	2000ft	175 deg
134224(39)	-134724(40)	Run 5.1	2700ft	355 deg

ABORT AT THIS LEVEL

35515(43)-135951(44)	Run 6.1	5800ft	360 deg
140116(45)-140551(46)	Run 6.2	5800ft	175 deg
140708(47)-141143(48)	Run 6.3	5800ft	355 deg
141305(50)-141746(52)	Run 6.4	5800ft	175 deg
142101(54)-142526(55)	Run 7.1	7500ft	360 deg
142700(56)-143126(57)	Run 7.2	7500ft	175 deg
143256(58)-143721(59)	Run 7.3	7500ft	355 deg
143853(60)-144319(61)	Run 7.4	7500ft	175 deg
144319(61)-144422(62)	Run 7.5 (sampling cabin air)	7500ft	175 deg
144847(63)-145347(64)	Run 8.1	100ft	360 deg
145506(65)-150007(66)	Run 8.2	100ft	175 deg
150137(67)-150638(68)	Run 8.3	100ft	355 deg
150808(69)-152422(70)	Profile P3	50ft->FL90	100 deg

163627

Land at FARNBOROUGH

Aircraft Scientist Debrief: A297

Variation of Aerosol/CCN Composition and Concentration VACC

Flight A297 was carried out on 12 November 1993. The sortie was relatively successful, with problems being experienced with the ASASP-X laser towards the end of the flight.

The sortie was carried out to the West of Ireland. Beyond a frontal system which was moving Easterly. Behind the front we found moderately high wind and no precipitation. The measurements were carried out in a region of very small Cumulus clouds.

The problems with the laser was not determined during the flight and it was decided to check the system out in the laboratory before the next flight.

SORTIE BRIEF: 12 NOVEMBER 1993

Variation of Aerosol/CCN Composition and Concentration VACC

- 1) **SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To determine the vertical structure of sea-salt and non-sea-salt sulphate aerosol in a clean marine boundary layer.
- 2) **LOCATION:** Northeast Atlantic, ^{53N 12W} ~~54N 11W~~. The sortie will be conducted directly up-wind of (and in the same air mass as) the Mace Head ground based research station.
- 3) **WEATHER:** Non-precipitating, moderate to high wind region in the cyclone system tracking across the N. Atlantic. Air trajectory must be purely maritime.
- 4) **FLIGHT PATTERN:**
 - a. Transit over Ireland to sampling location and approx 20K ft (2hr 10min)
 - b. Execute a profile to ^{50ft if pos} 200ft in cloud free air, if possible, @ 1000ft/min then, once in the marine boundary layer, profile @ 500ft/min (30min)
 - c. Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min)
 - d. VACC horizontal runs will be conducted at (1) ^{TP 100ft.} 200ft above sea-level (25min), (2) just below cloud base (25min), (3) ^{500ft} ~~400ft~~ above cloud base (25min) and (4) above cloud top (25min). Each VACC run will comprise two figure-of-eight race tracks across wind direction (total of four 5-minute legs, one for each heater tube, and a one minute turn). If a decoupled marine boundary layer exists, then an extra VACC run (25min) will be required just above the surface-subcloud layer inversion. VACC runs in cloud will depend on cloud size. In between VACC run profile at 500ft/min
 - e. On completion of stack, terminate the scientific part of the flight with a profile down to ^{50ft} ~~200ft~~ @ 500ft/min (30min).
 - f. Transit back to base (^{1hr 10} ~~1hr 50min~~)

TOTAL DURATION Transit 4 hrs
 VACC 3-3.5hrs

Request diplomatic clearance to transit over Ireland

AIKRAF T SCIENTIST 3 LOG

Aircraft Scientist: ANDREW KAYE

Project: VITEC Date: 12/11/13

Flight No: 1297 Page 1 of 7

11.40
190
14 Kts
10 to
and
Spast
30st
dec.
58 mwa
170
118

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:15:28	00	TR	21.4		260			1/8 ci above hazy w broken cu below.	
11:27:25	01	TR	21.9	P	309			clear above broken cu below in streets. fog visible in valleys.	
11:37:	03	R1	22.0	A	306			clear above bands of cu. fog in valleys.	
103845	03	R1	21.8	A	285	52.00	-3.36	4/8 broken cu below some streets.	
104545	03	R1	21.8	A	282	52.09	-4.57	5/8 broken cu below. small clouds.	
105540	03	R1	21.8	A	288			in haze sky? larger thin. broken cu below	
11:58:09	03	R1	21.9	A	289			just skimming the top of the ci. 4/8 broken cu below	
110355	03	R1	21.9		292			cu to south below 4/8 north below clear. front penetrating out? still in thin layer.	
11:09:27	03	R1	21.8		289	52.51	-7.65	to ci & nothing visible above or below	
11:22:48	09	R1	21.9		277	52.76	-9.11	out of ci solid cloud above and below	
11:24:26	04	R1	21.9	A	280	-9.30	52.75	solid cloud above and below very lumpy.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: ANDREW KAYE

Project: VACC Date: 12/11/93

Flight No: A297 Page 2 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:31:07	07	P1	21.5		295	52.87	-9.19	hazy ci above sc below some large gaps	
11:39:00	07	P1	17.3		290	53.01	-10.60	ci above just skimming the tops of cu layer	
11:43:13	07	P1	14.8		288			into cloud	
11:44:03	07		14.5		278	53.09	-11.03	out of cloud ci above SE below	
11:54:27	07	P1	8.9		255	53.13	-11.78	sc below ci above small cu to North.	
11								cloud to 6500 ft.	
12:05:00	07	P1	0.9		232	52.83	-12.45	7/8 sc cu above	
12:06:15		P1	50ft		231			Sea state 4	
12:11:36		R2	100ft R		345	52.81	-12.42	8/8 sc above. —	
12:17:40		R2.2	100ft		3165	52.96	-12.49	9/8 sc above.	
12:22:41		and R.22	100ft					7/8 sc above some sun patches visible.	
12:24:15		R.2.3	100ft		347	52.65	-12.40	6/8 sc above. 285 knots wind.	

7/10
 750
 21000
 52000
 8000
 3 1/2
 5000
 75
 6-6
 clear
 0490
 001

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: VNCC

Date: 12/11/93

Flight No: A247

Page 4 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:07:14		end R3.3	1000	P	344	52.74 -12.35	4/8 st cu above.		
13.08.37		R3.4	1000	P	164	52.73 -12.39	2/8 st cu above Ci above that Hazy.		
13.13.43		end of R3.4	1000	P	166	52.47 -12.27	7/8 st above.		
13:15:30		P2	2000	F	B44				
13:15:57		R4.1	2000	P	348	52.49 -12.13	Sc above 20300 ft below cloud base		
13:20:58		end R4.1	2000	P	348	52.72 -12.21			
13:27:35		end R4.2	2000	P	217	52.44 -12.15	now raining unprecipitated.		
13:28:36		R4.3	2000	P	346	52.44 -12.18	5/8 st cu above Hazy below Ci sheet above.		
13:33:33		end R4.3	2000	P	244	52.68 -12.26	3/8 st cu above some clear sky Ci 6/8 cu above.		
13:34:55		R4.4	2000	P	167	52.63 -12.30	5/8 st cu above.		
13:39:57		end R4.4	2000	P	162	52.37 -12.14	into cu.		
13:42:20		R5.1	2700	P	332	52.40 -12.03			

1740
1740
1830
1623

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kemp

Project: JKCC Date: 12/11/93
 Flight No: A247 Page 5 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13.47.29		5.1	280	P	17	52.60	-12.22		
13.48.36		5.2	469	P	170	52.58	-12.15	very broken cloud on this Run. about clear below, ci above.	
13.55.13		6.1	345	P	345	52.37	-12.07	in cloud 5200 ft above base 5300 7300 -> out top	
13.59.52	end	6.1	5.8 345	P				in and out of broken cu.	
14.01.19	start	6.2	5.8	P	168	52.57	-12.12		
14.05.50	end	6.2	5.8	P	216	52.33	-11.97	Many layers of cloud difficult to clearly identify	
14.07.08		6.3	5.8	P	345	52.37	-12.04	in and out of cloud	
14.11.43	end	6.3	5.8	P	345	52.52	-12.10	in and out of broken cu. ci above haze below.	
14.13.05		6.4	5.8	P	167	52.59	-12.14	into cloud.	
14.17.46	end	6.4	5.8	P	166	52.33	-11.95	6's in below 5's cir above	
14.20.41		7.2						end of profile	
14.21.00		7.1	7.0	P	349	52.34	-12.08	6's in below with some banking ci above.	

1520
 1400
 500
 100
 6 1/2
 7/2

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kuyk

Project: H 247 Date: 12/11/93

Flight No: WACC Page 6 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14.25.26		7.1	7.6		302	52.61	-12.11	ci - above lower layers of bc below	
14.27.00		7.2	7.6		164	52.56	-12.10	§	
14.31.27	end	7.2	7.6		166	52.34	-11.89	thin sc str bands below thin 8/8	ci above
14.32.55		7.3	7.6		345	52.36	-11.97	7/8 sc below # ci above	
14.37.23	end	7.3	7.6		347	52.00	-11.99	clear directly below sc above of below	7/8 ci above
14.43.20	end	7.4	7.6		344	52.33	-11.80	1/8 cu below ci above	
14.44.22	end	7.5	7.6		161	52.28	-11.70	ci / cu above 2/8 cu below.	
14.48.46		8.1	100	L	348	52.44	-11.64	state 4 seen some cu sc and ci above	
14.53.47	end	8.1	100	R	348	52.00	-11.72	x	
14.55.06		8.2	100	R	162	52.02	-11.73	1/8 sc above § ci above that. see state 4	
15.00.17	end	7.2	100	R	162	52.36	-11.59	1/8 sc above § ci above since look vis through	
15.01.37		4.3	100	R	347	52.37	-11.66	looks in vhrz equip.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *VITEC* Date: *12/11/93*

Flight No: *A247* Page 7 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
<i>15:02:37</i>		<i>end 8.3</i>	<i>100ft</i>	<i>R</i>					
<i>15:07:</i>		<i>P3</i>	<i>50ft</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>91</i>	<i>5</i>		<i>some cu visible 3/4 to starboard 8/8 ci above.</i>	<i>1040</i>
<i>1520.30</i>		<i>P3</i>	<i>7000</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>81</i>	<i>-</i>		<i>cloud top 7000 ft P</i>	
<i>1522.07</i>		<i>P3</i>	<i>7.8K</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>77</i>	<i>-</i>		<i>8/8 Sc below 5/8 ci above sky visible but not to the Port</i>	<i>Permitted</i>
<i>15.24.25</i>		<i>end P3</i>	<i>9.0</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>96</i>	<i>-</i>		<i>in a cloud</i>	
<i>15.31.59</i>		<i>T Mon</i>	<i>20.6</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>104</i>	<i>52.58</i> <i>-9.09</i>		<i>in cloud.</i>	<i>58</i>
<i>16.08.43</i>								<i>out of cloud 25K → 9K decent @ 2000 ft/min.</i>	<i>60</i>
<i>16 10:34</i>		<i>Thore</i>	<i>16400</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>106</i>	<i>51.68</i> <i>-2.84</i>		<i>high approaching severe squall. scattered bands of cu. Sc above. sky on the horizon</i>	
<i>'6:15:00</i>		<i>Thore</i>	<i>8700</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>115</i>	<i>51.59</i> <i>-7.34</i>		<i>high below bands of cu ahead. Sc above.</i>	

HDG deg T 309.	SPR mb 431.	PHGT kft 21.8	TAS knots 304.	TAT C -38.9	DEW C -44.8	WIND deg m/s 264/14
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

CLIMB OUT OF FARNBOROUGH.

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
304.	432.	21.8	292.	-39.0	-41.3	280/13

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

CLIMB OUT OF FARNBOROUGH

PCASP CONC/cc

100

0

PCASP CONC #/cc 2
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.07
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.00

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LHC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.4
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LHC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 10:54:15

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
 1000

1
 1

0.1
 0.1

10
 10

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 2
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.08
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.01

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 1.8
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.4
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 10:55:28

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

PCASP COUNT	FSSP COUNT
1000	
1000	
1	10
1	10

SE

0207 12-NOV-93 10.57.96 053 0.00 0.00 FL P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
289.	431.	21.9	311.	-38.6	-38.8	293/20

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

going into the Cirrus

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC	#/cc	1
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.05
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	0.00
FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.0
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00
2D-C CONC	#/l	0.8
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-12 11:03:26

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 14
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.59
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 34.81

FSSP CONC #/cc 1
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 6.1
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 71.8
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 300
 2D-C LWC g/m3 4.216e-002

93-11-12 11:12:34

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
 1000

1
 1

0.1
 0.1

10
 10

PCASP CONC/cc

500

PCASP CONC #/cc 40
PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.10
PCASP MASS ug/m3 1.40

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
FSSP MEAN RAD u 1.8
FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 11:37:50

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 124
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.09
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.52

 FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 0.0
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

 2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 11:48:43

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

3.01

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 59
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.09
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.25

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.9
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 11:57:18

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A297

12-NOV-93

12:06:51

008 Ω

52.78 -12.53

RV P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
228.	1010.	0.1	181.	10.3	3.3	289/ 9

SE DF

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

407

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 166
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.10
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 2.86

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.7
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 12:09:05

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
81.	1004.	0.2	187.	9.3	5.5	290/8

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

500

0

PCASP CONC #/cc 140
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.11
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 10.09

FSSP CONC #/cc 1
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.8
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 12:22:01

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1 0.1 10
 1 0.1 10

PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 172
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.10
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 3.29

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.7
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 12:39:25

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

HDG deg T 344.	SPR mb 976.	PHGT kft 1.0	TAS knots 179.	TAT C 7.4	DEW C 3.1	WIND deg m/s 301/8
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SPR mb 976.17 DEW C 3.13

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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0297

12-NOV-93

13:04:39

026

Ω

52.63

-12.31

FR P

HDG deg T 343.	SPR mb 976.	PHGT kft 1.0	TAS knots 187.	TAT C 7.6	DEW C 2.5	WIND deg m/s 293/10
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A SELECT	B	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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PCASP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 59
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.10
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 0.68

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.7
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 13:44:27

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

HDG deg T 347.	SPR mb 817.	PHGT kft 5.8	TAS knots 195.	TAT C -3.1	DEW C -3.0	WIND deg m/s 257/17
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A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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FSSP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 105
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.17
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 37.60

FSSP CONC #/cc 12
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 5.7
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.01

2D-C CONC #/l 0.5
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 13:59:26

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

A297

12-NOV-93

14:06:45

046 Ω

52.33 -12.00

RV P

HDG deg T 306.	SPR mb 819.	PHGT kft 5.8	TAS knots 193.	TAT C -2.7	DEW C -4.9	WIND deg m/s 264/18
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SE OF

FLINE OF

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

FSSP CONC/cc

PCASP CONC #/cc 131
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.47
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 283.61

FSSP CONC #/cc 9
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 8.6
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.03

2D-C CONC #/l 2.9
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

93-11-12 14:17:02

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

A297 12-NOV-93 14:19:24 052 -- 52.27 -11.98 AS P

250. 787. 6.8 203. -3.3 -9.7 262/20

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT		FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A297

12-NOV-93

14:52:00

003

32 52.50

11.00

TR 1

HDG deg T 345.	SPR mb 1009.	PHGT kft 0.1	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 9.9	DEW C 3.6	WIND deg m/s 303 / 8
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SE OF

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T 80.	SPR mb 755.	PHGI kft 7.9	TAS knots 202.	TAI C -5.4	DEW C -20.4	WIND deg m/s 255/19
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CLAT 0.00 CLONG 0.00
deg deg

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A297 12-NOV-93 15:25:09 070 -- 0.00 0.00 A5 P

100. 689. 10.3 201. -9.8 -10.6 252/26

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PROFILE P3

HDG deg T 98.	SPR mb 634.	PHGT kft 12.4	TAS knots 204.	TAT C -14.6	DEW C -15.2	WIND deg. m/s 248/25
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PROFILE
P3 544-FL90

FSSP CONC/cc

100

0

PCASP CONC	#/cc	28
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.15
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	13.54

FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	0.0
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	3.3
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

93-11-12 15:28:54

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

0297 12-NOV-99 15:33:24 078.0 52.56 -0.94 FR

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
106.	449.	20.9	276.	-28.9	-27.3	278/39

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAMS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP Reff

A297 93-11-12

version 5.1 15:39:42

FSSP corr 1.00

H297 12-NOV-93 10:25:33 070 32 51.50 -1.15 FR P

HDG deg T 124.	SPR mb 912.	PHGT kft 2.9	TAS knots 256.	TAT C 3.0	DEW C -7.5	WIND deg m/s 238/10	
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

SMUK-IE EGRR
 12 NOV 1993
06Z

NAUTICAL MILES SCALE 1:250,000
 GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 1MB INTERVALS

12 NOV 1993 AT 06Z

SMEW EGRR
12 NOV 1993 AT 06Z

LOW 06Z

DATA CUT-OFF TIME: 6.41

LOW

12 NOV 1993 AT 06Z

AS XX EGRR 112000Z 00E

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:2000

100	200	21
85	205	20
80	215	21
70	205	20
60	215	22
50	230	22
40	230	28
30	210	32
25	220	31
20	245	34
15	245	34
10	225	52
MAX	NIL	

100	225	14
85	250	22
80	255	21
70	260	19
60	280	23
50	280	26
40	265	27
30	275	25
25	265	35
20	265	35
15	265	34
10	255	27
MAX	60MB	
	260	60

100	210	17
85	250	33
80	270	22
70	250	21
60	255	27
50	305	38
40	290	39
30	270	34
25	275	38
20	280	50
15	265	30
10	260	22
MAX	NIL	

100	230	17
85	235	37
80	230	32
70	240	34
60	235	46
50	255	42
40	230	31

100	245	17
85	255	24
80	265	28
70	270	28
60	265	25
50	270	21
40	270	30
30	305	51

100	250	11
85	240	17
80	250	18
70	255	22
60	265	24
50	305	31
40	300	35
30	235	31

LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z
10-55
15-54
20-52
T 307-56

100	230	17
85	235	37
80	230	32
70	240	34
60	235	46
50	265	42
40	265	51
30	290	61
25	285	64
20	290	53
15	275	41
10	270	43
MAX	9694	
	285	78

RUGHTON
03322
AT 11Z
10-56
15-54
20-55
T 338-53

100	245	17
85	255	24
80	265	28
70	270	28
60	265	25
50	270	21
40	310	30
30	305	41
25	295	39
20	300	52
15	295	49
10	270	29
MAX	NIL	

HEMSBY
03496
AT 11Z
10-54
15-53
20-52
T 321-53

100	250	11
85	240	17
80	250	18
80	255	22
70	255	23
60	265	24
50	305	31
40	300	35
30	295	31
25	285	32
20	285	33
15	260	37
10	240	30
MAX	NIL	

VALENTIA
03953
AT 11Z
10-57
15-55
20-55
T 300-55

100	205	24
85	215	41
80	215	44
80	230	45
70	240	46
60	250	47
50	270	48
40	290	49
30	305	102
25	300	118

CAMBARNE
03608
AT 11Z
10-57
15-55
20-55
T 272-55

100	255	16
85	250	20
80	255	18
70	285	20
60	290	17
50	320	35
40	315	69
30	320	111
25	320	103

HERSTHONCUM
03882
AT 11Z
10-56
15-53
20-50
T 322-53

100	245	9
85	250	16
80	250	18
80	265	17
70	255	24
60	265	24
50	285	27
40	285	31
30	295	36
25	290	38

002 FRI 17/N/93

REL. HUMIDITY.
HEIGHT DM.

70000
70000

002 FRI 17/N/93
TIME 05.45.31 CHART 65

ISOTHERMS KT.
HEIGHT DM.

30000
30000

PHEA30 EGRR 00007